

Just-In-Time Learning: using Skill Trees to connect Challenge-Based Learning to fundamental skills

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Abstract

The amount of Challenge-Based Learning (CBL) applied in university curricula is growing. A common pitfall when using CBL is that the projects are disconnected from the fundamental theory and skills (e.g., mathematics) that students learn. This results in missed learning opportunities as well as a reduced motivation for students.

This paper presents a solution to this problem using Skill Trees. Skill Trees are an educational tool that allow teachers to plan which skills students need to master, when they need to master it and how they can work towards said mastery. The application to Project-Based Learning, in which all students have a similar project, is still relatively straightforward with little effort required from the teacher. An extension concerns the application of Skill Trees to CBL, where project topics can widely differ. Here the teacher needs to play a more active role coaching student groups. In both cases, the result is a Just-In-Time Learning set-up that more strongly connects fundamental skills and theory to applied project work.

Interviews with students have indicated both an increased motivation as well as a stronger mastery of fundamental skills, as compared to using CBL without just-in-time teaching.

Keywords: Challenge-Based Learning, Knowledge Graphs, Skill Trees, Just-In-Time Learning, Course Structuring

Introduction

In recent decades, STEM education has seen a shift from traditional classroom learning towards learning in projects. Instead of only learning basic skills, students are tasked with solving more practical problems. The idea is that this grows the students' confidence of applying their skills in practice. (Allan, 2007; Taconis and Bekker, 2023)

There are many variations to exactly how to set up such a project. Is the project part of a course, or a separate course? Is theory taught to students separately, or do they need to figure it out on the go? Are the problems to be solved simulated, or from an actual company? And do all student groups get the same/a similar task, or is there a wide variety of topics? Though the literature is not unanimous on the naming (Sukacké et al., 2022) we will consider *Project-Based Learning* (PBL) as having a mostly simulated project, with fixed scope, often coupled to theory, while *Challenge-Based Learning* (CBL) is more broadly scoped, often with assignments from actual companies, where students have to figure out for themselves what skills are needed to tackle the challenges at hand.

A key element of PBL/CBL is that students apply the skills they learned. Ideally this is coupled: students learn a skill and quickly afterwards they get to apply it in practice. This

Just-In-Time Learning (JITL) set-up increases both the motivation of students to learn, as well as the retention of the skill. (Abdulwahed and Balid, 2009; Killi and Morrison, 2015) In practice, this direct connection is often much less present. In many curricula the theory courses and project courses are developed separately. Students complain that they don't know why they're learning the theory they are learning. By the time they get to the project, a large part of the obtained knowledge is forgotten. (Gallagher and Savage, 2022)

To reduce this disconnect, a new competency-based didactic method called Skill Trees has been used to couple fundamental skills to their application in PBL/CBL courses. In this paper, we first briefly present this method. We consider how we can apply it in PBL/CBL courses in general and then look at actual applications in courses. In the end we evaluate these applications to derive lessons learned.

Structuring educational content through Skill Trees

To couple educational contents to projects, it helps to structure the respective contents. In particular, we want a method that deals well with competency-based content: modelling what students can and cannot do. Ideally suited for this are Skill Trees. These are defined and explained in more detail in (Bijl, 2025), but the main definitions and ideas will be summarized here.

The fundamental component behind the Skill Tree is the *skill*: a range of actions that are deemed similar enough to make them comparable. A skill can have a variety of *exercises* associated with it: a challenge of doing a certain action, with requirements to verify if it was done in a satisfactory way. Exercises can typically be split up into steps. Each of these steps are then again exercises, which could each be coupled to other skills. This gives us the *subskills* of the respective skill: a skill *A* is a subskill of a skill *B* if executing *A* is commonly a significant step in executing *B*. By visualizing the links between all skills, we find the so-called *Skill Tree*: a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) whose nodes are skills and whose edges are prerequisite relations between the skills. An example is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: An example Skill Tree (simplified) around the skill *Solve linear equation*.

Coupled to Skill Trees are Concept Trees. A *concept* is an idea or definition (or combination thereof) that one can visualize or have an intuitive grasp of. Commonly a concept is a notional machine (Du Boulay, 1986; Sorva, 2013). We say that a concept A is a *subconcept* of a concept B if grasping this concept A is directly necessary to grasp concept B . The overview of all concepts is the *Concept Tree*: a DAG whose nodes are concepts and whose edges are prerequisite relations between the concepts. Concept Trees and Skill Trees are connected, since skills often also require concepts. The converse is not true: concepts never require skills.

Using Skill Trees as tool to plan courses

Suppose that we have developed a Skill Tree for a set of theory. How can we use it? There are three distinct cases that each have their own challenges and possibilities.

In *classical education* there are generally no projects. Education focuses on the fundamental contents. In this case, having a Skill Tree is mostly beneficial for lecture planning: the Skill Tree helps teachers plan in which order to teach concepts/skills and how to divide these subjects over class sessions. On top of this, Skill Trees help teachers and students track progress. By noting each student's mastery level for each skill and visualizing this in the Skill Tree, teachers and students can immediately see how far along each student is. This progress tracking can be done in a variety of ways, from a simple 'You have done three exercises correctly, so you have mastered this skill' up to a more elaborate probability-based tracking algorithm. (Bijl, 2024) Either way, having a clear overview of progress helps motivate students in their studies.

Skill Trees become more useful in the case of *Project-Based Learning* (PBL). In PBL there is generally a mostly predefined project, with pre-determined schedules and steps. In many curricula, a PBL project is often coupled with a theory course; either as two separate courses, or as one joint course together with the project. In this case the Skill Tree can help the theory course in teaching the right contents at the right time. If the project requires students to have mastered (for example) the skill *Solve linear equation* in week 4, then the theory course can immediately see which prior concepts and skills need to be taught, ensuring sufficient mastery at the right moment. Doing so may seem like common sense, but in practice this rarely occurs to a sufficient degree and having a tool like a Skill Tree makes this matter more concrete and visual, facilitating the *Just-In-Time Learning* (JITL) process.

The application of Skill Trees in the case of *Challenge-Based Learning* (CBL) is even more powerful, but also more challenging. In CBL courses, the project is usually not clearly defined in advance and with an (often) external stakeholder involved, the skills needed to successfully tackle the project are unknown in advance and will differ per project group. In this case, having a Skill Tree of all contents that may be relevant for the project is even more beneficial. If students, in consultation with their supervisors/coaches, for instance decide 'We must apply a regression analysis' then with the help of a Skill Tree they can see all the subskills they need to learn to be able to apply such a regression analysis. In this case teachers take more of a coaching role, advising students what they

need to study, while the students take charge of their own learning, following the learning path they plotted for themselves. The Skill Tree serves as the map where they plot the learning path. Students decide on their own timeline – what they need to know when – in true JITL fashion.

A simplified example of a study plan based on a Skill Tree is shown in Figure 2. Here a student has decided to master a skill J in four weeks' time. The Skill Tree shows ten skills (or identically concepts) that need to be mastered to get there. For the first week, the goal is to master skill C, which also requires skills A and B. For the second week the focus is on mastering E. The third week is about getting to H. The fourth week then allows the student to master J, just in time for its application in the project.

Figure 2: An example Skill Tree used to plan what needs to be learned in JITL fashion. Skills are grouped into blocks (e.g., weeks) based on intermediate targets (asterisks).

Application in practice

The above ideas have been applied at the Institute for Design and Engineering of the Utrecht University of Applied Sciences. Specifically, there have been three places in the curriculum where the Skill Tree methodology has been applied, each in one of the ways described above. We will study their application to show the experiences learned.

The first application concerns the first-year courses of the *Mechanical Engineering* bachelor. The first year is split up into four quarters (15EC each) and each quarter has three courses (5EC each). Two of each quarter's courses are theoretical courses, of which one focuses on STEM (mathematics, physics, etcetera) and the other on related theory (design theory, material sciences, etcetera). The third course is a project course, formally called *Professionalization*. In the past, all courses operated independently of each other and a common complaint from students was that they didn't see how the mathematics they learnt was relevant to what they did. To fix this, the following steps were taken.

1. The theoretical courses formalised/visualised their structure using Skill Trees.
2. The project courses identified the skills they needed in their projects and which weeks these skills were required/applied.
3. The theoretical courses adjusted their schedules to teach these skills directly prior to the respective application.

The restructured schedule worked well at showing students why they learned certain fundamental skills. Agreeing on these connections between courses helped teachers refer to each other's courses, 'You will need this for your project course next week.' It also facilitated students at using the language they learned in their theoretical courses within their project, 'We just have to calculate the *cycle efficiency*, like we learned in class.'

The second application concerns a master course *Data Science*, part of the master *Next Level Engineering*. This 5EC course was set up based on PBL. The course consisted of two parts: theory and project work. The theoretical part was taught in two-hour lectures on Mondays, after which students had to do a few basic exercises to master the presented skills. (First collecting/cleaning data, then setting up a classification/regression/clustering algorithm and finally analysing the developed algorithm to answer the business question.) Each of the lectures used Skill Trees to outline the skills that were taught and how they related to each other. For the second part of the course – the project – student groups (of up to four students) had to define their own Data Science project, subject to various requirements. These requirements ensured that the project was of sufficient depth and that it fit well with the schedule in which the theory was presented. In practice some students chose projects more focused on classification (week 4) while others chose projects requiring more regression (week 5), so not all topics were equally used by each group. Wednesday's classes were used to coach the project groups on their progress. The final grade was partly (50%) based on the project work (written group report) and partly based on each student's theoretical understanding (individual oral exam).

The third application concerns a third-year bachelor course with the (translated) title *Create: Creation of new products and processes*. In this course, students were tasked to design and develop a new product, including a detailed analysis of how it would work in practice. (Think of mechanical stress tests, vibration analyses and more.) There were companies providing potential projects, but students could also define their own projects or use examples provided by teachers. Topics and scales could vary significantly, ranging from a tiny part of a robot arm to a city-wide energy distribution network. Also the timeline varied, with some groups mostly doing design work, while others developing various prototypes. To ensure that students would have access to the right theory, the course offered a large set of potential modules that the students could learn through self-study. Students were not required to do all modules (there would be too many) but decided themselves, in consultation with teachers, on what would be useful to learn for their project. Part of the project reflection revolved around how the theory learned was used within the project. Though there was a minimum amount of modules that needed to be done, many students surpassed this minimum. The final grade was based on the full portfolio of students, which included both small module assignments (individual, often auto-graded) as well as project work (in groups, manually graded).

Results and conclusions

To check the impact of the implemented changes, the course evaluations and course pass rates have been examined and focused interviews have been held with both teachers and students. We will discuss the results of each of these investigations below.

For cases 2 and 3 (Data Science and Create, both new courses) the respective courses consistently had the highest student evaluation ratings in their respective programs. This shows that students generally appreciate the set-up. For case 1 (Professionalization, an existing course) the evaluation ratings were on average somewhat higher than before Skill Trees were used to connect projects to theory, but the differences were small and there were also various outliers, especially during the corona pandemic.

The pass rates for all courses have in general been good. Especially worth noting is that the Create course (case 3) replaced a variety of theoretical courses with traditional exams. These exams always had a relatively low pass rate, resulting in some students being 'stuck' in their curriculum because they lacked one course still needed to graduate. The self-study modules and their exercises, on the other hand, worked a lot better for students. They could take their time to do this well, not being subject to the time pressure of exams. This effectively solved the problem of students being stuck in their studies.

In focused interviews, teachers have mainly noted the differences in type of work. For case 1 the differences weren't very pronounced, but for case 2 and especially case 3 the role of teacher has shifted more from 'provider of knowledge' into 'project coach'. Most teachers indicated that, while this new role comes with more uncertainty/improvisation and is hence more challenging, it is also far more rewarding since there is a lot more in-depth contact between teacher and student. Workload-wise there was not much of a difference. In case 3, a large amount of work went into setting up all self-study modules, but afterwards this effort paid off and resulted in a workload reduction.

Students have indicated in interviews to be positive about the changes. Most students appreciated not having the stress of exams anymore, as well as doing work more connected with practical applications. In case 3 students mentioned they needed some time to get used to the idea of setting own learning goals, but most students found it a far more satisfying experience. A minority of students preferred the classical set-up, 'Just tell me what to study and I'll study it.'

The opinions of students and teachers on the use of Skill Trees have generally been positive. In cases 1 and 2 most teachers found them a helpful tool in planning their course, while most students were ambivalent, 'It's nice to have a Skill Tree as an overview, but we need to study everything anyway.' For case 3 students were a lot more enthusiastic about the Skill Trees. Instead of needing a teacher to help them set up steps to reach certain learning goals, they could plan their own path, increasing their autonomy. 'Checking out all the modules and how they were connected was like planning a vacation. What would be fun and useful? And how do we get there?'

Overall we can conclude that methodically connecting theory to projects improves the learning experiences of students and Skill Trees are a helpful tool, both for teachers to facilitate this connection and for students to plan learning paths towards individual learning goals.

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